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Conservation and Management of Indian Built-Heritages: Exploring the Issues and Challenges

ARNAB GANTAIT*, PRIYAKRUSHNA MOHANTY** and G. ANJANEYA SWAMY***

*Arnab Gantait, Research Scholar, Department of Tourism Studies, Pondicherry University, Puducherry, India

**Priyakrushna Mohanty, Research Scholar, Department of Tourism Studies, Pondicherry University, Puducherry, India

***G. Anjaneya Swamy, Dean and Professor, School of Management, Pondicherry Central University, Puducherry, India

ABSTRACT

Heritage Tourism has emerged as a catalyst for economic growth thanks to its ability to create alternative jobs, induce developed infrastructures and increase the flow of both domestic and foreign tourists which result in regional as well as national growth. India, a country blessed with remarkable natural and manmade heritages has welcomed this niche form of tourism with open arms. However, as a consequence of negligence and lack of proper management skills, the sustainability of these monuments is at cross roads. Improper heritage-awareness, lack of coordination among the stakeholders, inadequate funding as well as paucity in understanding the growing demands have further contributed to the sad state. Therefore, conservation, preservation, sustainability and enhancement of these heritages remain the top most priority of the country. Based on the experiences of NGOs and review of major works in the area of heritage management and conservation, this paper puts light on the overall status of heritage sites and monuments in India and also tries to find out the emerging challenges in heritage preservation in this country. Moreover, this paper outlines major strategic mechanisms required to overcome these constraints to preserve our cultural heritages which are nothing but the true reflection of our rich cultural past.

KEYWORDS: *Heritage, Heritage Tourism, Heritage management, Heritage Preservation, Economic Development.*

Introduction

Since time immemorial, India has been widely acknowledged for its intriguing, fascinatingly rich and diverse heritages which are nothing but the strong reminders of its glorified ancient history. The celebrated past and cultural diversity of this nation have created a potent blend for attracting millions of tourists every year. Therefore, the rise of heritage tourism in India was quite long anticipated and as expected, this new form of niche tourism has registered a significant growth in Indian tourism market in past few years. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) defines 'Heritage' as "our legacy from the past, what we live with today, and what we pass on to the future generations" whereas, 'Cultural Heritage' has been described as, "the irreplaceable sources of life and

inspiration that include monuments such as architectural works of monumental sculpture and painting, elements of structures of an archaeological nature, inscriptions, cave dwelling and combinations of features; groups of buildings, groups of separate or connected buildings; and sites including archeological sites having outstanding historical, aesthetic, ethnological or anthropological value”.

Heritage may it be any cultural or natural product or built asset always draws attention of the tourists and motivates them to visit those particular sites to personally experience it. It has been commonly observed that every time a new form of tourism evolves and progresses, it not only unlocks many socio-economic opportunities for the host community but also helps that particular destination in terms of destination rebranding and repositioning. Dwyer, Forsyth & Spurr (2004) also supports this view by saying that “heritage tourism has a positive impact on local economy”. Therefore, if ‘Heritage’ and ‘Tourism’ both can be managed properly, the overall benefit of ‘heritage tourism’ would be maximized that can facilitate both the host as well as the guests at a particular destination.

The term, ‘Heritage Management and Conservation’ refers to a constant and active process that involves proper maintenance and protection of heritage elements from being shattered or restored without proper management, control, and appropriate methods. Subsequently with the passage of time, India, a nation enriched with its history and tradition is losing its heritages one after another. Many of its historic monuments and sites are now in bad shape as a result of continuous negligence and lack of heritage awareness; both pointing towards an overall hesitation at all levels while taking necessary measures to manage and preserve these heritages in long run. In this context, Timothy & Nyaupane (2009) opines that “in spite of the constantly growing interest in cultural-heritage tourism, the body of knowledge is still young and this knowledge is essential for the management and preservation of heritages in developing countries.”

Based on the review of major works in the area of heritage management and conservation, this paper puts light on the overall importance of heritage sites and monuments in India and tries to find out the emerging challenges in heritage preservation in this country. Moreover, this paper outlines major strategic mechanisms required to overcome these constraints to preserve our cultural heritages which are nothing but the true reflection of our rich cultural past.

Study Objectives

The study revolves around three key objectives. The first objective is to highlight the role of heritages in the socio-economic development of the county. For the second objective, the paper provides a detailed discussion on account of the issues and challenges faced by Indian heritage tourism. The third and the final objective deals with providing suggestive measures to uplift the Indian heritages from its sad state and restore its integrity.

Research Methodology

The research is descriptive in nature and qualitative approach has been taken to understand the intrinsic issues involved in heritage management and preservation. The authors have reviewed and analyzed the media reports, published works, research papers, working papers published in the area of heritage management and preservation. Moreover, NGOs working in the field of heritage management, preservation, and conservation were consulted to gather resourceful insights. The

thematic and content analyses were also being used to scrutinize and infer the data acquired from report reviews and experts responses. In addition, the researchers have visited many places to gain the practical experience and have interacted with the local community, tourists, tourism stakeholders, and few officials to make a detailed report.

Heritages and Socio-Economic Development

Heritages are of perennial importance to the development of any country. They are not only the guardians of the past, but also are a major catalyst in inducing socio-economic growth in country. They are also known as the agents for instigating innovative capacity of knowledge. This Section of the work deals with the heritage-led socio-economic developments of a nation.

Economic Implications of Indian Heritage Tourism

Heritage tourism has proved itself a fast growing and high-yielding sector. Over the past twenty years, the popularity of Heritage Tourism has been growing with the number of travelers and with new tourism attractions. In India the scope of heritage tourism market is expanding day by day.

Table 1 : Circle wise Number of Domestic Visitors to Centrally Protected Ticketed Monuments in India (2013 to 2015)

Circle	2013	2014	2015
Agra	8278404	8706910	10373368
Aurangabad	3848777	3962232	4253537
Mumbai	2463882	2835332	3177878
Bangalore	2121728	2300499	85608
Bhopal	1654763	1905602	1975079
Bhubaneswar	2965921	2874356	3325122
Chandigarh	134056	163367	198670
Chennai	1529588	1361538	1319570
Delhi	7829436	8433501	9855921
Dharwad	2351162	2378443	2464727
Guwahati	331873	337491	401346
Hyderabad	3272237	3639561	3661315
Jaipur	713821	851320	924962
Kolkata	1239452	1296819	1427706
Lucknow	818972	853031	908428
Patna	1818792	1844688	2176614
Raipur	64800	72601	83985
Thrissur	555199	316918	652226
Vadodara	1023268	1076713	1111673
Srinagar	53437	74847	75174
Shimla	117161	140090	163634
Grand Total	43186729	45425859	48616543

Table 2 : Total No. of Domestic Tourists to Centrally Protected Ticketed Monuments in India (2013-2015)

Year	Domestic Tourists visit Centrally Protected Monuments	Total No. of Domestic Tourists visited India	Share (%)
2010	35770242	747703380	4.78
2011	40534481	864532418	4.69
2012	43259075	1045047536	4.13
2013	43019998	1145280443	3.75
2014	45425859	1281952255	3.54
2015	50988730	1431973794	3.56

Table 3 : List of India's Most Lucrative Heritage Monuments, Based on the Revenues Earned in 2013-2014

Indian Heritage Monument	Approx. Revenue Earning (INR)
Taj Mahal, Agra	21,84,88,950
Qutab Minar complex, Delhi	10,16,05,890
Agra Fort, Agra	10,22,56,790
Humayun's Tomb, Delhi	7,12,88,110
Red Fort, Delhi	6,15,89,750
Group of monuments, Fatehpur Sikri	5,62,14,640
Group of monuments at Mahabalipuram	2,72,93,480
Sun Temple, Konarak	2,43,52,060
Group of temples, Khajuraho	2,24,47,030
Ellora Caves	2,06,72,820

Table 4: Total No. of Visitors to Centrally Protected Ticketed Monuments in India (2005-2015)

Year	Number of Visitors			Annual Growth Rate		
	Domestic	Foreign	Total	Domestic	Foreign	Total
2005	21035864	2122436	23158300	3.3	18.7	4.6
2006	23815252	2250502	26065754	13.2	6	12.6
2007	23450419	2614254	26064673	1.50	16.2	0
2008	28786608	2679763	31466371	22.8	2.5	20.7
2009	30321981	2165346	32487327	7	18.10	4.9
2010	35770242	2998175	38768417	16.1	36.6	17.5
2011	40534481	2948065	43482546	13.3	1.70	12.2
2012	43259075	3064778	46323853	6.7	3.9	6.5
2013	43019998	2995852	46015850	0.60	2.20	0.70
2014	45425859	2792272	48218131	5.6	6.80	4.8
2015	50988730	2620228	53608958	12.2	6.20	11.2

Source for Table 1, 2, 3 & 4: Ministry of Tourism, Govt. of India. (17202) & Past

Issues

Here, Table 1, Table 2, Table 3, and Table 4 all are reflecting the growing market for Heritage Tourism in India, as there is a paradigm shift in tourists' attitude and their demand and it has become a core global trend in travel and tourism industry, where the travellers are expecting their trips to be more experiencing and educative compared to the conventional holiday trips where the scope for learning new things is very limited. Recently few studies have disclosed that the heritage tourists generally spend higher at per day basis and usually stay longer period of time at any particular destination compared to other kinds of travelers.

Heritage as National Identity

Culture is conceived as the mirror of humanity (Kottak, 2005) and heritages are nothing but the historical record and understanding of the spirit of people in terms of their values, works and actions.

It consists of all aspects with regard to the man-made historic environment, monuments, built infrastructure, physically created places and archaeological sites with immense historical significance.

There is a deep connection in between heritages and the native people as heritages are their cultural identity and civilizational legacy to the world. John Henrik Clarke, an American historian once rightly said that people's relationship to their heritages is as similar to the relationship of a child to his/her beloved mother. Steinbeck (2007) affirmed Clarke by raising a very relevant question, "How will our children know who they are if they don't know where they came from?" Günlü, Pınar, & Yağcı (2009) opines that "heritage records and expresses the processes of historic development forming the essence of diverse national, regional, indigenous and local identities and it is the tangible links between past, present, and future." The relevance of the heritages and taking responsibility to protect them for the future generations, acclaimed recognition first time in 'Venice Charter for the Conservation and Restoration of Monuments and Sites', in the year of 1964 (Singh, 2011). According to, Johnson & Thomas (1995), the promotion of heritage sites for heritage tourism is important from the perspective of the development of national identity.

For centuries, people from different geographical locations with their respective cultures, ethnicity, religion, values, and languages migrated into India and later on mixing with its aboriginal culture, customs and rituals they have given birth to a new color of cultural heritages.

As one turns the pages of history, India's sage-old rich culture inevitably comes alive with all its fragrance and it is still breathing in its splendid architectures, minutely carved motifs and embellished facades of the monuments, those are fringed in every possible corner of this multi-facet country. These cultural heritages have always been the illustration of wealth and power of this country and serve as the backbone of tourism development in India.

Table 5: Centrally Protected Ticketed Monuments in India (Circle-wise List)

Circle	Centrally Protected Monuments
Agra	Taj Mahal; Agra Fort; Fatehpur Sikri; Akbar Tomb; Mariyam's Tomb; Itimad-ud-Daula; Ram Bagh.
Aurangabad	Ajanta Caves; Ellora Caves; Pandaulena Caves; Daulatabad Fort; Bibi-Ka-Maqbara; Aurangabad Caves.
Mumbai	Elephanta Caves; Kanheri Caves; Karla Caves; Caves-Temple & Inscriptions, Junnar; Raigad Fort; Shaniwarwada; Hirakota Old Fort; Old Fort Sholapur; etc.
Bangalore	Group of Monuments, Hampi; Daaulat Bagh; Srirangapatnam; Keshva Temple, Somnathpura; Tipu Sultan Palace; Chitradurga Fort; Bellary Fort; etc.
Bhopal	Western Group of Monuments, Khajuraho; Shahi Quila at Burhanpur; Royal Complex, Rani Roopmati Pavilion, Hoshang Shah Tomb, Mandu; Buddhist Monuments at Sanchi; Gwalior Fort etc.
Bhubaneswar	Sun-Temple, Konark; Raja Rani Temple; Ratnagiri Monument; Udaigiri & Kandagiri Caves; Ratnagiri; Lalitagiri.
Chandigarh	Sheikh Chillis Tomb Thanesar; Suraj Kund Monastery, Lakarpur.
Chennai	Group of Monuments, Mamallapuram; Rajgiri & Krishangiri Fort; Fort Dindigul; Moovarkoil, Kalumbalur; Rock Cut; Jain Temple, Sittanvasal; Natural Cavern, Eladipattanam; Fort Thirumayan; St. George Fort, Chennai Gingee Fort; etc.
Delhi	Jantar Mantar; Rahim-Khane-Khanam Tomb Delhi; Purana Quila; Sultangahri Tomb; Tughluqabad Fort; Safdarjung Tomb; Red Fort; Humayun Tomb; Qutab Minar; Sultanghari's Tomb etc.
Dharwad	Durga Temple complex, Aihole; Caves at Badami, Group of Monuments at Pattadakal; GolGumbaz, Bijapur;; Jaina & Vaishna Caves at Badami; etc.
Guwahati	Ahom Raja Palace, Gurgaon; Karanghar Palace, Sibsagar; Ahoma Raja's Palace, Garhgaon; Rangghar Pavillion, Sibsagar; Vishudol, Joysagar; etc.
Hyderabad	Golconda Fort, Golkonda; Charminar, Hyderabad; Fort, Raja & Rani Mahal Chandragiri; Ruined Buddhist Stupa & Remains Amarvati; Hill of Nagarjunakonda; etc.
Jaipur	Deeg Palaces, Deeg; Kumbhalgarh Fort; Chittaurgarh Fort.
Kolkata	Kooch Bihar Palace; Hazarduari Palace Museum Murshidabad; Bishnupur Group of Temples.
Lucknow	Rani Jhansi Mahal, Jhansi; Sahet of Shrivasti Monument; Rani Jhansi Kila, Jhansi; Residency, Lucknow; Kalinjar Fort
Patna	Sarnath; Site of Mayuran Palace, Patna; Vaishali; Jaunpur Fort; Nalanda; Man Singh Observatory; Sasaram Shersshah Suri Tomb; Lord Cornwallis Tomb, Gazipur; Remains of Patliputra, Kumrahar, Patna; Excavated Site Vikramshila, etc.
Raipur	Laxman Temple, Sirpur.
Thrissur	Bekal Fort Pallikkare; Mattancherry Palace Museum Kochi.
Vadodra	Sun Temple Modhera; Rani-ki-Vav, Patan; Monuments at Champaner;

Circle	Centrally Protected Monuments
	Buddhist Caves, Junagadh; Ashokan Rock Edict, Junagadh Baba Pyare and Khapra; Kодиya Caves, Junagarh.
Srinagar	Ram Nagar Palace, Ramnagar; Group of Temple, Kiramchi; Avanti Swami Temple, Avantipura; Leh Palace, Leh.
Shimla	Kangra Fort, Kangra; Rock Cut Caves, Masoor.

Source: Ministry of Tourism, Govt. of India. (17202) & Past Issues

But, only possessing the monuments is not enough. The importance we place on our sense of identity and culture reflects in how we manage, protect and care for our heritages those are the testimony of our ancient predators. No law, no rule, no force can save our monuments if there is no awareness regarding the significance of their existence.

Heritage and Tourism Interdependency

From extensive literature review, it has been found that there is a close connection in between 'Heritage' and 'Tourism'. According to **Bushel & Jafari (1996)**, the relationship between tourism and cultural-heritage is not a 'newly formulated concept'; rather it can be addressed as a 'newly advocated concept'. **Herbert (1995)** considers the 'attractiveness of heritage in the form of a commodity' as an important reason behind the growing number of areas to be promoted as heritage destinations now a day. **Dann (1981)** opines that the cultural heritages are one of the major inspirational factors for traveling in different period of time.

Reisinger (1994), **Hargrove (2002)** both argue that the heritage sites often make the visitors nostalgic as they reflect the true culture of the host community and have direct links with their glorious past. **Devesa, Laguna, & Palacios (2010)** also considers heritage monument sightseeing as one of the significant motivating variables for the cultural visitors. It is now an established fact that visiting these historical places, monuments, sites having great archaeological value brings socio-economic and environmental benefit through generating tourism revenue, exchange of thoughts and culture in between the host and the guests, and safeguarding the natural and man-made heritages at local, regional and national level. Thus it would not be an exaggeration to say that prosperous future of 'heritage' and 'tourism and travel' both depend on each other.

In this connection, India is also not an exception as this country has always been considered as a unique land with rich culture and heritage. Every time a tourist visits India, he/she gets a glimpse of India's past through the elaborate superfluities and wonderful architecture of the Indian monuments those are also the guardian pillars of India's cultural heritage. These splendid samples of unbelievable artistry covering a sense of mystery, deception, and romance are the evidence of the master craftsmanship and elegance that brings the splendor of the bygone era to the forefront and always astound the visitors. Therefore, the management aspect of both Indian heritages and Indian tourism should be well taken care of.

Heritage Tourism: An Advocate of Sustainability

Reisinger (1994) defines Heritage Tourism as "visits to historic buildings, sites, museums, art galleries, etc." **Garrod & Fyall (2001)** considers it as a tourist activity in a place with the availability of historic artifacts. **The National Trust for Historic**

Preservation defines this new form of niche tourism as “a trip to experience the places, artifacts and activities those authentically represent the stories and people of the past and present.” **Tighe (1986), Hardy (1988) and Millar (1989)** all suggest that it is “all about the cultural traditions, place, and values that groups throughout the world are proud to conserve.” In 2002, the World Tourism Organization (WTO) executive Luigi Cabrini stated that “the worldwide trend is clearly showing that heritage tourism is growing faster compared to any other forms of tourism” (**Parker, 2007**). This statement has been supported by **McCain & Ray (2003)**, who affirm that Heritage tourism has gained a substantial growth in the tourism industry in recent years. According to **Günlü, Pirnar & Yağcı (2009)**, Heritage tourism is gaining importance day by day not only for its economic benefits to the society as it injects new money into the economy, diversifies the local economy by creating new jobs, promotes the preservation of local resources, encourages the development and maintains the community amenities, but also for its more sustainable approaches that include social and environmental benefits in terms of enriching social capital, promoting local culture, building relationship among and within the local people, improving community pride, creating enjoyable opportunities both for the host and the guest and finally boosting awareness regarding the importance of heritage monuments and sites. Heritage tourism also certifies the recognition of any noteworthy element that is important enough to be preserved and maintained with proper care and supervision so that, these elements can be passed on to the future generations. UNWTO has already acknowledged tourism as a potential tool for poverty alleviation and community development. The data reveals that more than 50% of the total number of UNESCO’s World Heritage Sites (a total number of 1073) are located in the developing countries and in last two decades a constant growth has been observed in case of international arrivals in these countries and one of the many reasons behind this increased travel demand is nothing but the presence of these cultural built-heritages in the form of tourism resources.

Issues Involved and Challenges Faced

After realizing the cultural and economic significance of heritages that is happening slowly in India, the people, the tourism stakeholders, the government bodies etc. have started paying more attention in its preservation but still, there are many hindrances, those are bothering the preservation initiatives. Academicians, Conservation Architects, Reporters have pointed out many of these challenges in their articles, interviews, and reports and raised a common voice to adopt a proper Heritage Management and Conservation policies and process to make these heritages secured for the long run. International communities like UNESCO, ICOM, and ICOMOS are also showing deep concern to protect these cultural-heritage monuments (**Biswas, 2002**). The American Art historian, Bonnie Burnham, heading ‘World Monuments Fund’, has rightly said, “Tourism carries a tremendous potential that must be acknowledged as essential for the future of world heritage. But without proper management, we can easily get out of control.” Therefore, to identify or to highlight these management challenges in heritage preservation is very much important. Here the researchers have minutely read a good number of scholarly articles and newspaper reports on the context of Indian heritages and its preservation challenges; visited few prominent heritage spots and interacted with scholars, academicians, conservation architects, tourists, local community people

and finally have identified the following emerging challenges of heritage preservation in Indian context.

Problem of Recognition and Supervision of Indian Built-Heritages

Indian built-heritages are the most valued gift to the entire humanity. However, these heritages are scattered throughout this country. Therefore, it is essential to recognize these properties so that they can be properly supervised and maintained. In India, The ASI under the provisions of the AMASR Act, 1958, protects its monuments, sites, and remains of national importance. As per their record, there are more than 3,500 ancient monuments, archaeological sites and remains exist in India whereas, UNESCO has recognized only 36 sites as 'World Heritage Sites'. Apart from these India have thousands of monuments those are architectural marvels but have not been enlisted even in state, regional national heritage lists. It is a shocking truth that, Archaeological Survey of India (ASI) also confessed that a total number of 35 protected monuments are "Untraceable". Fig. 1 is showing the details. The inclusion of these cultural heritages will obviously draw the attention greater number of tourists that can help the regions to earn more tourism revenue that could be spent on their own individual renovation work or maintenance.

Figure 1: List of India's Historic Misses

Source: Times of India Published: Apr 7, 2013, 02.49 AM IST

Lack of Interest in Heritage Maintenance from all Level

The total number of state protected monument is only little more than 3,362 all over the country and therefore, there is a fair possibility that other unrecognized monuments might be converted into ruins or vanished due to lack of maintenance measures in a long run. According to the statistical data, the total number of unprotected monuments/sites in India is 75,307 (Time Period 2007-2012). It is also being observed that in many places, there is still lack of interest in local Government level and in the private bodies to show interest in taking care of heritages or in

investing money for the sake of heritage conservation and maintenance. Moreover, legal hurdles, public apathy, the lack of government intervention have led to the rapid deterioration of heritage structures in many places.

Figure 2: No. of State protected Monuments in India

Source: http://asi.nic.in/asi_protected_monu_list.asp

Figure 3: No. of Unprotected Monuments in India (State/UT-wise), Time Period: 2007-2012

Source: Lok Sabha Starred Question No. 88, dated on 20.03.2012.

Dearth of Persistent Lobbying and Tenacious Effort to Grab World’s Attention

Despite having the rich treasure of cultural objects, several countries in the world have more ‘World Heritage Sites’ because of the dearth of persistent lobbying by the Indian Government, ASI, and other national organizations. It has been observed worldwide that inclusion of any site in UNESCO’s ‘World-Heritage List’ always helps that place to become a major tourist attraction. Though India has one of the most ancient cultures, this country is very poor in international participation as out of 1052 WHS all over the world, it has only 36 to date. Fig: 6 shows countries like Italy, Spain, France, and Germany those are smaller than India (in area size) possesses more World Heritage Sites (WHS).

Figure 6: India has Less Number of World Heritage Sites compared to Even Smaller European Countries

Source: <http://whc.unesco.org/en/list/>

Lack of Comprehensive Development Planning

Heritage monuments like Jagannath Temple in Odisha and cluster of monuments in Hampi, Karnataka are facing continuous negligence from the host community and local administrations while adopting a comprehensive development plan. Many consider that if the ancient heritage monuments were being surrounded with landscaped grassed flowered parks, its beauties might have enhanced several times. However, many of the recently constructed heritage monuments like Somnath Temple in Gujarat are being ruined by the uncontrolled and haphazard growth of shops, restaurants, human residences, illegal constructions etc. in its periphery.

Encroachment

May it be the (a) land encroachment by immigrants or by local authorities, or the (b) monumental or residential or commercial encroachment; the Indian Government and ASI both have failed abjectly in both cases to control the proliferation of encroachment cases in heritage sites. The encroachers have opened their shops, business establishments etc. in Sanchi, Khajuraho, Gwalior, Mandu, and Chanderi like popular heritage sites in Madhya Pradesh state. In Assam, over 7,000 bighas belonging to 39 Satras (Mahapuruxiya monasteries founded by the great Bhakti Saints Mahapurusha Srimanta Sankardeva in the 15th century AD) those are at the centre of Assamese culture are facing serious encroachment. Kobaikota Satra, one of the 800 odd monasteries set up since Srimanta Sankardeva began his Vaishnavite movement in Assam in the 16th century, has lost most of its land due to encroachment by immigrants. In Delhi, encroachments have dwarfed many of the monuments established during the period of Sultanate and Mughal dynasty. Residential buildings have mushroomed up around many heritage monuments. Delhi Gate finds itself threatened by new construction. The Fatehpur Sikri complex is in the threat of mining mafia. Other historical remnants like Jodhabai's Chatri, Jaswant Singh ki Chatri, Chini ka Roza, Humayun's mosque, Mariam's tomb, Babar's Ram Bagh, Barakhambha, Jama mosque are also in danger, as encroachments creep up on every inch of space. The Agra Development Authority is responsible for ensuring the monuments encroachment-free but during interviews, conducted by many newspaper reporters, the officials have confessed that the demolition of all illegal constructions is even beyond their capacity. In Telangana, the 'Kakatiya Heritage Property Protection Committee' has urged the district administration to

prevail over the land grabbers who have intruded on the heritage lands around the historic Padmakshi temple (Source: The Hindu, May 10, 2016). Srirangapatnam, Karnataka, notified by the state government as 'heritage town' in 2005 for its cultural, natural and spiritual richness is losing its charm as the places surrounding its forts, monuments, temples, fort gates etc., all have been encroached by commercial establishments and illegal constructions, and lack of concerns from the local government as well as its host community people at large (**Shankar & Uma, 2012**). Persistent encroachment on the premises of the temples is being cited as the reason for the gradual destruction in Odisha where once there were over 500 temples in Bhubaneswar, now the number is 70 only. Many of the major historical sites such as Khandagiri, Vaital temple, Chudangada, Swarnajaleswar, Amania temple, Barabati fort etc. have already been encroached upon by multi-storied buildings on its premises. In Jaunpur, Uttar Pradesh, the Shahi Bridge, one of its main heritages has been encroached by the makeshift shops of miscellaneous articles since the British period. Many of such monuments, protected under the ASI and State Archaeological Departments are still facing myriad problems. The souvenir sellers have covered the carvings of beautiful granite pillars of the Meenakshi Temple, Tamil Nadu with their shops. The same incident happens in Rameshwaram, Kanchipuram and several other temples of Tamilnadu.

Improper Heritage Management and lack of basic Tourists' Facilities

Another problem that is affecting many of the heritage sites in India is the absence of the proper solid waste disposal mechanism. Moreover, the basic tourists' facilities such as proper sitting arrangements, availability of drinking water, clean and eco-friendly toilets, trained professional guides, interpretation centers are also absent in many places. If more and more heritage resources can be connected with good infrastructure and tourism, these sites can even earn more revenue that will facilitate the local community and can be spent on overall destination development.

Pollution

Many scholars point out in their scholarly articles that the pollution is gradually increasing at different heritage sites and maximum pollutions are created by visitors and locals, who due to their apathy, negligence and lack of civic sense throw several types of biodegradable and non-biodegradable materials everywhere and unfortunately, many a time the authorities or the monitoring bodies also do not care proper disposal due to lack of interest, fund or priority. The grand marble of edifice of iconic Taj Mahal located in Agra, (the top revenue generating heritage monument in India that has earned almost 75 Crore INR in last three years as per the Report published in The Times of India, Jul 19, 2016, 14:17 IST) is slowly turning in brownish-yellow due to continuous air and water pollution in its surrounding areas as per the report compiled by the National Environment Engineering Research Institute, Hyderabad, and the tourism statistics is showing that the flow of foreign visitors to Taj Mahal is also on wane since last few years. The 400-year-old Charminar monument, located at the bustling bazaars of Hyderabad's old city is hit with the layers of dust on its structure. A study conducted by Vardhaman College of Engineering, Hyderabad found that the level of city's Total Suspended Particular Matter (TSPM) is among the highest in the area where this age-old heritage monument is actually standing. In 2013, Punjab Pollution Control Board (PPCB) conducted a collaborative study with the IIT, Delhi that concluded that the traffic,

the tandoors (ovens) from nearby restaurants and the industries are the main culprits for discoloring of the main building's facade and the golden plates affixed on the shrine at the Golden Temple, Amritsar in Punjab.

Light & Sound Shows

The Indian Tourism Development Corporation (ITDC) conducts light and sound programs at heritage sites with the purpose of highlighting the historical glory through an audio-visual medium. Such initiative is bringing more number of tourists to visit these sites but on the other hand, the intense light, high pitch of sound system, vibrations create cracks on the walls of these monuments as the light generates heat that harms the plaster works and the colors of monuments.

Vandalism

Some countries have made laws for the protection of cultural heritage. India is one of them. The Antiquity Act of 1947, Antiquities and Art Treasures Act of 1972 particularly provide for the prevention of smuggling and illegally dealing in antiques. In addition, the Ancient Monuments and Archaeological Sites and Remains Act, 1958 (No. 24 of 1958) says that, "if someone destroys, removes, injures, alters, defaces, imperils or misuses a protected monument s/he shall be punishable with imprisonment which may extend to three months, or with a fine which may extend to five thousand rupees, or with both." Then also the vicious trend of vandalism and destruction of heritage buildings and heritage sites is ongoing. The vandals are continuously damaging sculptures, gold/silver/bronze/stone made idols in many Indian temples and tourist places with immense historical value and the situation is deteriorating more and more by the idol smuggling rackets those are inscribing and taking out these idols out of the country. Moreover, the epigraphs are vanishing during the construction work of additional facilities in ancient temples and applying of the fresh coat of paint during its renovation. It is due to the negligence of watchmen in museums, monuments etc. No thefts is possible from museums, monuments or sites without the involvement of local party directly or indirectly.

Lack of Awareness and Community Participation

Shankar & Swamy (2013) considers Heritage awareness as a vital component of conservation. But, it is disheartening that the visitors often inscribe their initials, names, places, addresses or messages on the invaluable archaeological masterpieces those are nothing but our national treasures and it happens due to the lack of awareness regarding the cultural significance of such masterpieces. In addition, one of the major challenges in heritage conservation is to win the trust of local communities so that they come forward and cooperate as many a time it has been observed that many conservation processes have been stopped due to local resistance and such kind of challenge can only be overcome if the conservation plans and policies can benefit the local community people and it is not happening often in India.

Suggestive Measures for Heritage Conservation and Management

The previous section draws attention to the various issues and challenges faced by the Indian Heritage tourism sector. This portion of the paper outlines an array of strategic measures that must be adopted to preserve, conserve, sustain and enhance Indian heritages. They are;

- Better civic sense and a sense of responsibility instilled in the host community as well as the visitors towards the cultural heritages can prevent themselves

from scribbling on the walls of archaeological masterpieces. Therefore, spreading awareness about the importance of the heritage monuments is essential. In this connection, cooperation between the public and the private sectors is very much needed to start such awareness campaign in local and regional level. Moreover, Heritage interpretation can be provided at interpretation centers, museums, historic sites, botanical gardens, zoos, nature reserves, art galleries, etc.

- The awareness programs on heritage management and its preservation should be conducted by the city authorities at a regular interval so that it can ensure larger participation from all section of the society including host community, tourists, tourism stakeholders, investors, officials, owner of heritage properties.
- The 'Heritage Walk' concept can also be effective where community people, students, tourists can participate. 'Freedom Walk', Street Plays can be organized in heritage sites on all national level festivities so that people can gather in large numbers to celebrate the events and to understand its significance and respect pay homage.
- Local Students and local residents can be motivated for active participation in regular 'Cleanliness Drives' of the heritage sites adjacent to their residences.
- Active involvement of institutions, organizations, Corporate, Multinational corporations and individuals at the international, national and local levels to protect and preserve our common cultural heritage and share the financial responsibilities or being a part of the 'Adopt a Heritage' initiative.
- Local and state Government authorities should publish brochures, newspapers and books on topic regarding heritage conservations and they should disseminate these documents in schools, colleges, and universities, public residences to make the new generation people cautious about their own heritages.
- Meetings, surveys, reports, heritage clubs should be set up by schools, educational institutes to make students and youth aware to save monuments.
- Government and international organizations should conduct regular investigations to uncover the culprits and their supporters, involving in vandalism and other criminal offenses and to bring them to justice.
- Restrict the trade of illicit trafficking of antiquities in domestic and international level and Ban on purchasing of illicit antiquities from the market.
- There is a need of strong lobbying with concrete steps and arguments for the inclusion of the other heritage objects apart from the heritage elements those already have secured a place in the UNESCO 'World Heritage Site' list by proving 'outstanding universal value.' Many experts have opined that earning the coveted UNESCO tag would not only have ramped up the revenues but also help in keeping heritage free of encroachment.
- Displaying the ethnic products in the core heritage zone will benefit both the visitors and locals and it will generate the revenue that can be spent on heritage development.
- Many of the valuable arts, crafts, paintings and heritage buildings of the city are slowly disappearing due to urban expansion and city's growth. Therefore, it is to be suggested that to open an information center and museum to display city's rich heritage in the heritage area will benefit both tourists and locals.

- The officials, working in various departments related to heritage preservation and management, should be motivated to take participation in various workshops where their knowledge, skills and attitudes on heritage can be developed and enhanced.
- Heritage awards can be initiated to recognize the conservation efforts made by individuals, organizations, schools and media people.
- The government should start giving incentives, soft loans to the owner of heritage properties so that they can maintain old buildings having rich historical importance.
- Government should be stricter in taking action & plan to save monuments, setting up of Archaeological departments.
- Government, NGOs, and other organizations working in heritage preservation should give focus on collecting and generating more funds & donation for the renovation works.
- Taxes/donations to preserve monuments, monument fees and other related funds from citizens and tourists.
- Save our heritages from pollution by controlling mobs and keeping factories and other polluters away.
- The Area delineated as Heritage Area (depicted in the map) need to develop special plans for conservation and improvement of controlled areas.
- Alteration or demolition of any building is prohibited in the controlled conservation areas without the consent of the Planning Authority and Municipality as well.
- In order to preserve aesthetic environs around these monuments, it is necessary to declare areas surrounding these monuments as zones of special control.
- The encroachments are to be cleared and proper alternative arrangements are to be provided.
- Unite all organizations and supreme bodies those are directly and indirectly engaged in 'tourism' and 'management and conservation process of Cultural Heritage Properties' in India to form a single unit to function as an apex body to control Cultural-Heritage Tourism in India.
- Denying the 'Price of Visit' concept can create physical deterioration of heritage site because of funds paucity. Therefore, 'User Pay Principle' should be implemented at every heritage sites.

Conclusion

Every community and society has its own precious heritage, which has to be transferred to the coming generation and it is the responsibility of the civil society to transfer that heritage to the next generation. India has a rich heritage that includes a repository of archaeological treasures and incredible monuments and the cultural history epitomized in these heritage monuments stems from a historic past of its own ancient civilization. The number of these monuments and sites is so great that a single tour can't cover or discover the multifarious facets of this country. Therefore, being a responsible Indian citizen, it is our primary and pious duty to safeguard our ancient memorials and the preserved places having immense

historical significance and values and to ensure that no one can harm to them. We should also consider it our moral duty to maintain the purity virginity, sanctity, and beauty of these places. The Indian Government should involve Indian High Commissions/Embassies to enlist such heritage sites/structure within a stipulated time limit. This promotion of our heritages and the fund collection in term of donation for their maintenance and restoration can be executed by our diplomatic offices abroad. Moreover, the community, tourists, tourism stakeholders and operators should take more responsibility towards the preservation of our heritages those no doubt add an extra value to the prestige of India and the pride of every Indian.

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